

DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation

This article discusses the relevance of articles related to the development and popularization of information and communication technologies, as well as the digital world in all areas of our lives from the moment we spend our time to our ability to manage money. In addition, the article provides information on the basic principles of the digital economy, increasing efficiency and creating "digital enterprises".

Key words

Information and communication technologies, digitalization, HR, human capital, modern management, digital economy, big data, artificial intelligence, neurotechnologies, quantum technologies, internet of things.

Introduction

Today, articles related to the development and popularization of information and communication technologies around the world are becoming increasingly relevant. The revolutionary impact of ICT is reflected in government structures and civil society institutions, in the economic and social spheres, in science and education, in culture and in the way of life of people. This is due to the fact that in general, communication services make it possible to fully use the existing potential, to a large extent contribute to the achievement of the goals of sustainable economic growth, prosperity, democracy, peace and stability. In the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, important areas of economic development are identified. This Message also details the need and important benefits of the transition to a digital economy for the country due to the fact that 2020 has been declared the Year of Science, Education and the Development of the Digital Economy[10].

Indeed, the digital revolution, which is becoming a new stage in economic and technological development, has dramatically changed people's lives, created huge opportunities and increased competition in the international arena. Now such digital technologies as big data, artificial intelligence, neurotechnologies, quantum

technologies, cloud and mobile technologies, technologies of virtual and augmented reality, cross-exchange, blockchain technologies play a decisive role.

Analysis of relevant literature

Taking into account that the development of any activity is based on normative factors and legal means, this article also analyzes the constitutional rights of citizens to information and the execution of relevant decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the national legislation of Lex.Uz. In addition, the current aspects of the issues identified in the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis are listed. In particular, the theoretical basis of the payment system and its improvement in the process of digitalization are the works of foreign economists such as S.R. Bruu, V.V. Gerashchenko, V. Kolesnikova, O.I. Lavrushina, I.V. Larionov. In addition, some aspects of digitalization have been studied in the scientific works of such scientists as K.R. McConnell, D. Polfreman, E. Reid, P. Rose, D.S. Sinki, V. Usoskin. This article also analyzes data from Internet sources and relevant literature, and develops practical recommendations for their use.

Research Methodology

The methodological basis of this work was the legislative and regulatory legal acts on the development of digitalization processes in the country, in particular, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5349 "On further improvement of information technologies and communications" dated February 19, 2018. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP- 5953 "On the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021 within the framework of the Year of Science, Education and the Digital Economy" Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2017. In addition, the article uses modern statistical and observational methods used in the collection and processing of statistical data based on peer review and comparison. Also, graphical, analytical, structural analysis and other methods are widely used in the work. During the research it was revealed that:

External factors affecting the digital economy:

- increased competition at the international level;
- scale of investments and investment changes;
- innovative technologies;
- rapid development of information and communication technologies.

Obviously, these external factors affecting the digital economy include the international competitive environment, the scale of investment and its changing

conditions, the development of information and communication technologies, globalization processes and new innovative technologies.

Internal factors affecting the digital economy:

- scientific research and mechanisms for their stimulation;
- training and retraining of personnel;
- integration of practice and improvement of the quality of education;
- potential personnel who can work in innovative technologies.

The main internal factors influencing the digital economy include the development and retraining of personnel to acquire new knowledge, the quality and excellent incentives for research, the development of integration with practice in improving the quality of education, information and communication technologies and information security, mechanisms and anti-virus software, innovative technologies, as well as potential personnel who can work with them. The digital economy is a new economic environment that creates huge new business opportunities. In the digital economy, under the influence of new technologies of the digital economy and e-commerce, both the structure and nature of competition and business models are completely changing. For example, passenger market aggregators (GetTaxi, Yandex.Taxi, etc.) have made many changes in the activities of transport companies and managed to bring them closer to consumers. Food delivery companies have also made great strides in the competitive market by bringing suppliers closer to consumers. As a result, traditional offline companies are forced to transform their business or switch to an online mode. [1] This kind of situation encourages entrepreneurs to start their business on the Internet. Currently, there are completely online companies such as Amazon or Ozone, social networks, instant messengers, eBay, Avito or retail chains, online stores and logistics companies that have placed their e-commerce channels in a traditional offline business. The digital economy has provided businesses with the ability to generate new insights based on rapid business intelligence analysis and provide feedback to customers. This made it possible to have a reactive influence on the innovative expectations of potential customers. As a result of such work, such free services as Google Analytics and Yandex, Metrika were created. In addition, the digital economy is characterized by a significant reduction in the life cycle of innovations. This will lead to the rapid emergence of new versions of many new models of smartphones, computers, mobile applications, computer games. [2] According to scientists and experts, the emergence of new innovative transport systems is expected. For example, magnetic levitation vehicles, vacuum vehicles, Hyperloop systems, and others can be prime

examples of this kind of innovative transportation system. In addition, there will be the generation of innovative ideas using collective knowledge (mass cooperation, the sharing economy), the production of products and services, and the financing of new innovative projects. The sharing economy has changed the attitude of many members of society towards the possession of material goods. [3] For example, many young people in developed countries are not very interested in buying private property and owning it for themselves, because freedom of life, freedom of spiritual action and devotion to emotions, traveling the world, eco-tourism have become more important for them. The role of social networks in shaping the perception of a product or service by consumers is increasing more and more, because it is no secret that today work and communication in social networks have become an integral part of the life of all young people. New types of licenses for intellectual property (public licenses) have appeared. In this case, the rule of public ownership of the created product or service applies. Based on the foregoing, it is obvious that the digital economy is very important in the social environment. But it remains unclear what role their digital economy should play in the Republican program. First of all, due to limited resources, a decision will probably need to be made in which direction to focus efforts. Accordingly, society has two paths ahead: one is to engage in social adaptation of technologies, and the other is to increase local technological bases. [4,5]

Conclusions and offers

In conclusion, as the ICT sector and its tools are evolving at an ever faster pace, moving away from them is tantamount to moving one step forward and then two steps back. This is due to the fact that preparedness for global ICT challenges requires the creation of a transparent system through the digitization of public services and almost all sectors of the economy. In this regard, people are encouraged to start the digitization process on their own. For example, an entrepreneur engaged in small business and actively using ICT tools, saving his resources and achieving efficiency, will have an idea of how to develop web platforms for his activities, as well as create opportunities for the development and implementation of components of Digital Uzbekistan 2030 - a project with public participation. Not only entrepreneurs, but also people from all walks of life can take an active part in this, but the process of "digitalization" is carried out only by the public sector, which does not involve public figures, IT specialists in the private sector. For the further development of the digitalization process in Uzbekistan, attention should be paid to the following necessary aspects:

- further development of employees' skills and abilities in this area;

- improvement of training and retraining mechanisms, formation of a competitive environment in training centers;
- Increasing the speed of the Internet, reducing its cost and ensuring the information security of all enterprises and organizations;
- creation of an electronic accounting system at all enterprises and organizations;
- creation of software platforms for the development of priority sectors and sectors of the economy, as well as continuous improvement of the electronic system of public services.

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